

EFFECTIVENESS AND SAFETY OF PHYTOTHERAPY OF THE MEDICINAL PLANT - PAPAVER SOMNIFERUM L.)

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Relevance. Opium poppy, an annual herbaceous plant, is widely cultivated in southern Central Asia. Its petals contain 0.05% alkaloids and fatty acids. The greatest interest in studying this plant lies in its effects on the nervous system, exhibiting a sedative effect, as well as less pronounced hypnotic and analgesic properties. It is widely known for its hemostatic effect. An infusion made from the petals of the opium poppy is highly valued for its cough suppressant effect. Given its well-known beneficial pharmacological effects, the potential for adverse effects of the opium poppy cannot be ruled out.

Purpose of the study. The purpose of this study is to determine the effectiveness of opium poppy therapy and at the same time to define precautions for herbal medicine.

Materials and methods. The main resources we used in our study were a textbook on clinical pharmacology, articles devoted to the anatomical and morphological structure of the opium poppy plant, and a chemical-toxicological analysis of the constituents of opium poppy.

Results. In this study, we examined the characteristic properties of opium poppy, as well as its pharmacological effects on human organ systems. Its widespread use in folk medicine is based on its diverse chemical composition. Its effectiveness against coughs is due to the codeine it contains, which facilitates expectoration. It is recommended to use a mixture containing opium poppy petals. This mixture also has an expectorant effect. Due to its nervous system depressant properties, opium poppy is considered a powerful pain reliever. Its effectiveness can also be demonstrated in the treatment of insomnia. The danger of opium poppy, as a poisonous plant, is manifested in overdosing on medications made from it. For safety reasons, it is recommended to avoid using opium poppy-based medications in cases of general exhaustion for pain relief and respiratory failure. The use of opium poppy carries a significant risk of cardiac arrhythmia. General contraindications to the use of opium poppy-based medications include liver damage, children under two years of age, and the elderly. Opium poppy and alcohol are considered ineffective combinations, so alcoholism is a contraindication. The effects of concomitant use of certain medications with opium poppy-based medications should also be considered. For example, lopinavir prolongs the elimination of opium poppy-based medications, while tocilizumab, conversely, reduces the elimination of opium poppy alkaloids.

Conclusions. 1. Based on our research, we can conclude that the effectiveness of medications made from the opium poppy plant is greatest only when administered in the correct dosage.

2. To ensure safe use of opium poppy, it is necessary to take into account the general condition of the patient, age, gender, bad habits, condition of the liver, respiratory and cardiovascular systems.